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Review Paper

A GENERAL OVERVIEW OF HYDROGEL FOR ANTI-AGING TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogels are considered one of the newest frontiers in biomedical and cosmetology sciences due to their unique structural, mechanical, and biological characteristics. Other attractive properties that give hydrogels widespread applications in cutaneous uses include high retaining water capacity, biocompatibility, and controlled releasing action of therapeutic agents. Hydrogels are used for applications that include wound healing, drug delivery, tissue engineering, and anti-aging cosmetics. Hydrogel formulations in dermatological applications render hydration to the skin, stimulate collagen production, and sustain cell regeneration, empowering them to combat the visible signs of aging effectively. Development of hydrogel systems that are responsive to thermoresponsive, pH changes, and/or enable nanoscale particles provides sustained and targeted delivery systems for active compounds such as peptides and growth factors thereby improving treatment effects with reduced side effects. Despite challenges in production, sterilization, and clinical translation, novel research in nanotechnology, polymer science, and responsive biomaterials is modifying the way facile, personalized hydrogel therapies are being developed. Hydrogel thus is going to be a game-changer during the next generation of healthcare and cosmetic treatments, envisioning a sustainable, effective, and patient-based approach.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The skin's aging is attributed to various factors that can be classified as internal (cellular metabolism, hormonal alterations, and genetic mutations) and external (toxins, chemicals, or solar UV radiation) [1]. Aging is characterized by a decline in collagen production, further magnifying skin sagging, thinning, and wrinkling [2]. Biologically, aged skin shows a generalized decline in the various components of the extracellular matrix (ECM) and is characterized by disorganized and lesser collagen and elastin [3]. Another factor associated with the aging of the skin is inflammatory phenomena, which lead to wrinkling and thickening of the dermis and epidermis [4].

Hydrogel-based delivery systems are very much positively considered for application in dermatology and cosmetology because of their high water content and biocompatibilities, which produce a very cooling and soothing effect. The most favorable systems are, therefore, in skin care applications. This will act as a matrix for the active ingredient to be incorporated to ensure their controlled release and

enhanced penetration. Many hydrogels will swell and shrink through different pH, temperature, and ionic concentrations. The polymers are developed by blending monomers, whereas the hydrogels themselves are naturally biodegradable, with low toxicity. During degradation, they release harmless fragments, thus mimicking and supporting biological processes.

Water uptake capacity or swelling characteristics of hydrogel can easily change the hydrogel in response to environmental conditions such as temperature, electric signal, pH, or presence of enzyme and other ionic species. Biocompatible features: Biocompatibility is the activity of a material for appropriate host response in a certain context. Thus, biocompatibility comprises two primary elements: (a) bio-functionality i.e. the ability of material to perform the specific task for which it is intended. (b) bio-safety i.e. appropriate host response not only systemic but also local (the surrounding tissue), the absence of mutagenesis, cytotoxicity [11].

Fig no .1: Applications of Hydrogels in Cosmetics

Fig no: 2 Hydrogels: Types, Properties & Uses

- **Applications :(7)**

Table no.1: Different types of hydrogel cosmetic products available in market:

Product Name	Manufacturer	Hydrogel Form/Characteristics	Application	Reference
Rose Soothing Hydrogel Mask	Moira	Face mask made with sodium polyacrylate, glycerine, cellulose gum, water, etc., with maximum absorption. Soothes and rejuvenates the skin.	Face Skin	
Collagen Hydrogel	Dr. Derm Professional	Hydrogel contains sea collagen and hyaluronic acid. Nourishes, regenerates the skin of the face.	Face Skin	("Bulgaria website")
Advanced Genifique Hydrogel Mask	Lancome Paris	Hydrogel face mask made up of glycerine, polyacrylate-13, water, etc., enriched with Bifidus extract. Skin becomes moisturized, radiant, smoother, and looks healthy.	Face Skin	("Lancome website")
Charcoal Hydrogel Under-Eye Mask	ELF Cosmetics	Under-eye mask contains water, charcoal, seaweed extract, etc. Nourishes and gives a healthy glow to the skin.	Under-Eye Skin	("Elf Cosmetics website")
Lip Patch	Taiki	Hydrogel patch contains sodium hyaluronate and glycerine for moisturizing. Strong adhesion and gives lips elasticity and hydration.	Lips	("Taiki Cosmetics website")

Aloe Vera Supple Skin Hydrogel	Images	Sheet mask contains hyaluronic acid, glycerol, water, etc. Moisturizes, nourishes, smooths the skin, and also gives elasticity and firmness.	Face	("Images website")
Neutrogena® Hydro Boost®	Johnson & Johnson	Face mask contains hyaluronic acid. Provides instant and long-lasting moisture to the skin.	Face	("Neutrogena website")

Table No: 2: Commercially available hydrogel wound dressing single form:

Product Name	Company Name	Composition	Applications	Reference
ActivHeal®	Advanced Medical Solutions Ltd.	Primary wound dressing, contains 85% water	Pressure ulcers, leg ulcers, diabetic foot ulcers, cavity wounds	(Al Tabbaa and Ankrah, 2016)
DermaSyn®	DermaRite Industries	Primary wound dressing, contains Vitamin E	Acute or chronic partial and full-thickness wounds	("Dermarite website," -b)
NU-GEL™	Systagenix	Contains sodium alginate, effectively debrides necrotic tissue and fibrinous slough	Chronic wounds, diabetic foot ulcers, venous leg ulcers,	("Systagenix website,")

			pressure ulcers	
Purilon®	Coloplast	Contains calcium alginate and sodium carboxymethylcellulose with purified water	Leg ulcers, pressure ulcers, non- infected diabetic foot ulcers, first and second- degree burns	("Coloplast website,")
INTRASITE◇Gel	Smith and Nephew	Consists of carboxymethyl cellulose and propylene glycol	Pressure ulcers, diabetic foot ulcers, surgical incisions, venous ulcers	("Smith and Nephew website,")
SOLOSITE◇Gel	Smith and Nephew	Contains sodium salt of carboxymethyl cellulose and glycerol with over 60% water	Minor burns, cuts, abrasions, skin tears, venous ulcers, surgical incisions, diabetic foot ulcers, pressure ulcers	("Smith- Nephew Website,")
Woun'Dres®	Coloplast	Contains polymers like carbomer and collagen with other ingredients	Dry wounds	("Coloplast Website,")

2. MECHANISM OF ANTI-AGING HYDROGELS:

Extracellular matrix composition (e.g., collagen and elastin) declines in skin aging largely because of inflammatory phenomena [14]. Therefore, inhibition of skin cell ROS formation is critical for slowing down skin aging. Meanwhile, direct collagen upregulation is also one of the prime strategies for repairing skin cells from injury and hence for decreasing skin surface wrinkles [15]. Genomic instability manifests as permanent and transmissible changes in DNA sequence [16]. DNA damage caused by an inherently unstable genome includes spontaneous deamination, hydrolysis, and many other chemical changes such as different types of breaks, changes in base positions, gaps, DNA-protein cross-links, and other subtle chemical modifications [17].

It permanently and transmissibly changes the DNA sequence, i.e., a self-contained genomic instability [16]. It comprises spontaneous deamination and hydrolysis but also extends well beyond these to include things like breaks of various kinds, positional changes of bases, gaps, DNA-protein cross-links, and several other, more

subtle chemical changes-the general features of endogenous and spontaneous DNA damage arising from what has been called an unsteady or unstable genome[17]. Abnormal DNA structures, for example, G-quadruplexes, R-loops, and persistent single-strands, and abnormal intermediates in DNA transactions (for example, stalled transcription, replication, and recombination complexes), then are considered as DNA damage phenotypes. Thus, mutations in genome due to instability of DNA plays adverse effect on cellular activities, as well as being a major cause for cancer and other inheritable diseases [18]. However, it should be noted that instability in DNA is also important concerning the evolution of species. DNA has highly complex repairing and damage response (DDR) systems repairing damage over time from erosion and destruction: currently, we have maintained the integrity of DNA [19]. Another aspect of increased damage to DNA, causing the process of aging to speed up, is progressive shortening of telomeres. [20].

A large number of anti-aging materials have recently been proposed which are reported to enhance collagen synthesis. One of the well-known biomaterials is the growth factor.

Fig No.3: Skin Aging Mechanism

A large number of anti-aging materials have recently been proposed which are reported to enhance collagen synthesis. One of the well-known biomaterials is the growth factor. Growth factors have been thoroughly studied for skin wound healing [21] and many of them are directly involved in collagen synthesis by inter- and intracellular signaling cascades, including platelet-derived growth factor (VEGF), epidermal growth factor (EGF), and keratinocyte growth factor [22]. Although several studies have provided evidence that collagen synthesis is improved by topically applied growth factors and peptides, their single effectiveness in the induction of collagen synthesis without anti-inflammatory action may not be sufficient to bring about clinical improvements in anti-aging performance [23]. To enable more pronounced effects, the active agent

must penetrate deep into the layers of the skin. Hence, the urgent requirement is to develop new kinds of materials with dual activities, such as collagen synthesis verification and anti-inflammatory activities, combined with enhanced skin absorption capabilities [24].

3. TYPES OF ANTI AGING HYDROGEL:

1. Composition-Based:-

a. Natural Hydrogels –

The hyaluronic acid hydrogel is an extremely hydroxylated hydrogel, which assists with the plumpness of the skin by lessening the depth of wrinkles. Collagen hydrogel - Improves elasticity and cell regeneration. Chitosan Hydrogel - Has antibacterial properties for wound healing.

Alginate Hydrogel- Algal-derived hydrogel that shows moisture retention and calming effects [25].

b. Synthetic Hydrogel Polyacrylamide Hydrogel-

Used as fillers and cosmetics due to the water-holding capacity of these materials. Polyethylene glycol (PEG) hydrogel- This biocompatible hydrogel really has enormous potentials for controlled drug delivery. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogel-Very good moisture retention. It was previously called Osmosis Gel [26].

2. Function Based:

A. Hyaluronic Hydrogels-

- Deeply penetrates skin moisture to help minimize loss of trans-epidermal water.
- Contain hyaluronic acid, glycerin, and typically ceramides.

B. Hydrogel Drug/Active Loaded-

- Containing substances such as anti-aging retinol and peptides and vitamins such as vitamins C and Resveratrol or stem cell extracts.
- Provides more controllable release thus

longer-lasting efficacy.

C. Injectable Hydrogels-

- Dermal fillers (hyaluronic acid fillers) are made of these layers to volumetrically restore and mitigate wrinkles.
- May also accommodate growth factors or stem cells for skin regeneration.

3. The Delivery Mechanism:

A. Thermo responsive Hydrogel:

A type of hydrogel that is liquid at low temperatures and gel at physiological temperatures; in this way, it is promoting the deeper penetration of anti-aging compounds into the skin for therapeutic purposes.

B. pH-Sensitive Hydrogel:

- A release system with variable pH values of skin as a reference.
- Another means for localized treatment of aging or damaged skin.

C. Micro needle Hydrogel Patch:

- Contains a microstructure for enhancing penetration of anti-aging agents; typically loaded with peptides, hyaluronic acids, and/or vitamin C.

D. Hydrogel Modified by Nanoparticles Materials

Table No.3: Hydrophilic Polymers Used to Synthesize Hydrogel Matrices:

Category	Polymers	Reference
Natural Polymers and Their Derivatives (\pmCrosslinkers)		[30]
Anionic Polymers[30]	HA, alginic acid, pectin, carrageenan, chondroitin sulfate, dextran sulfate	[31]
Cationic Polymers	Chitosan, polylysine	[32]
Amphipathic Polymers	Collagen (and gelatin), carboxymethyl chitin, fibrin	[33]
Neutral Polymers	Dextran, agarose, pullulan	[34]
• Synthetic Polymers (\pmCrosslinkers)		[35]
Polyesters	PEG-PLA-PEG, PEG-PLGA-PEG, PEG-PCL-PEG, PLA-PEG-PLA, PHB, P(PF-co-EG) \pm acrylate end groups, P(PEG/PBO terephthalate)	[36]
Other Polymers	PEG-bis-(PLA-acrylate), PEG \pm CDs, PEG-g-P(AAm-co-Vamine), PAAm, P(NIPAAm-co-AAc), P(NIPAAm-co-EMA), PVAc/PVA, PNVP, P(MMA-co-HEMA), P(AN-co-allyl sulfonate), P(biscarboxy-phenoxy-phosphazene), P(GEMA-sulfate)	[37]
Combinations of Natural and Synthetic Polymers	P(PEG-co-peptides), alginate-g-(PEO-PPO-PEO), P(PLGA-co-serine), collagen-acrylate, alginate-acrylate, P(HPMA-g-peptide)	[38]

Table No.4: Methods for Synthesizing Physical and Chemical Hydrogels:

Type	Method	Reference
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Physical Gels		
Warm a polymer solution to form a gel	PEO-PPO-PEO block copolymers in H ₂ O	[39]
Cool a polymer solution to form a gel	Agarose or gelatin in H ₂ O	[40]
'Crosslink' a polymer in aqueous solution using freeze-thaw cycles to form polymer microcrystals	Freeze-thaw PVA in aqueous solution	[41]
Lower pH to form an H-bonded gel between two different polymers in the same aqueous solution	PEO and PAAc	[42]
Mix solutions of a polyanion and a polycation to form a complex coacervate gel	Sodium alginate plus polylysine	[43]
Gel a polyelectrolyte solution with a multivalent ion of opposite charge	Na ⁺ alginate ⁻ + Ca ²⁺ + 2Cl ⁻	[43]
Chemical Gels		
Crosslink polymers in the solid state or in solution with radiation	Irradiate PEO in H ₂ O	[44]
Crosslink polymers using chemical crosslinkers	Treat collagen with glutaraldehyde or a bis-epoxide	[45]
Use multi-functional reactive compounds	PEG + diisocyanate = PU hydrogel	[45]
Copolymerize a monomer + crosslinker in solution	HEMA + EGDMA	[46]
Copolymerize a monomer + a multifunctional macromer	Bis-methacrylate-terminated PLA-PEO-PLA + photosensitizer + visible light radiation	[46]
Polymerize a monomer within a different solid polymer to form an IPN gel	AN + starch	[47]

Chemically convert a hydrophobic polymer to a hydrogel	Partially hydrolyze PVAc to PVA or PAN to PAN/PAAm/PAAc	[48]
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Table No.5: Hydrogel Formulation Components

Category	Material
Hydrogel Base Polymers	Hyaluronic Acid (HA)
	Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA)
	Chitosan
	Alginate
Crosslinking Agents	Glutaraldehyde (GA)
	Genipin
	Calcium chloride (CaCl ₂)
Active Anti-Aging Compounds	Vitamin C (L-ascorbic acid)
	Retinol
	Peptides (Matrixyl)
	Resveratrol
Other Additives	Glycerol
	Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS)
	Deionized water

4. MATERIAL AND METHOD

(A) Methods:

1. Hydrogels' Fabrication-

-These are made out of a suitable mixture of polymeric constituents, like HA, PVA, chitosan or alginate.

-To prepare the polymeric solution, the polymeric material was dissolved in

deionized water at 60°C under continuous stirring until a homogeneous solution was obtained.

- Suitable cross-linking agents were incorporated dropwise under controlled gelling conditions to yield a stable gel matrix (GA, genipin, or CaCl₂).

2. Incorporation of Anti-Aging Agents-

- The aforementioned active materials, such as vitamin C, retinol, peptides, and resveratrol, also need to be incorporated into the hydrogel matrix during or after gel formation, in order to maintain this bioactivity.

- These active agents' entrapment efficiency into the hydrogel was determined by UV-Vis and HPLC.

3. Hydrogels Characterizations-

- Swelling Ratio: Hydrogel specimens were soaked in PBS at 37°C and an increasing weight was measured over time and mechanical property testing via rheological evaluations in rheometer (TA instruments).

- Morphology: Surface topography was done using scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL JSM-7500F).

- Biocompatibility: Cytotoxic assays on fibroblast (L929) cell culture were done using MTT assay.

4. Study Release In Vitro-

-The anti-aging agents were released in an in vitro Franz diffusion cell.

-Samples collected after defined time intervals and UV-Vis and HPLC were used for analysis.

5. Statistical Analysis –

-The data were analyzed by ANOVA and the significance was obtained at $p < 0.05$.

- All the experiments were performed in triplicate for the purpose of reproducibility.

5. APPLICATIONS OF ANTI-AGING HYDROGEL:

These fields are really interesting; tissue engineering and regenerative medicines[49]. Many applications for drug and tissue-targeting and all related but due to specific properties, hydrogels have gotten much attention. They simulate the natural ECM and offer a 3D microenvironment to influence cell behavior and tissue regeneration.

Tissue engineering is a discipline in biomedical engineering that links cells with engineering and materials for the repair and maintenance of different types of tissues. The biomaterials, therefore, need to possess not only the appropriate biochemical properties but also the matching physical and chemical ones. Micronized hydrogels are utilized in loading macromolecules into the cytoplasm of antigen-presenting cells. Commonly applied natural hydrogels for tissue engineering include methylcellulose, agarose, and hyaluronic acid and other naturally-derived materials [50].

Fig No.4: Applications of Hydrogels in Biomedicine

1. wound healing

The cross linked structure of hydrogels enables them to absorb water and drug as well [51]. Therefore, they can hold and retain exudates from wounds because of the holding water capability. Wound dressings are polymeric materials like gauzes, gels, hydrogels, hydrocolloids, etc. Among

these, hydrogels are the most promising ones in the wound healing process. The character of hydrogels, which makes them ideal for dressing wounds, is that they can provide a moist atmosphere at the wound site, help in the removal of exudates, prevent infection, and provide a proper environment for tissue regeneration [52].

Table No.6: Comparison of Hydrogel-Based Wound Care Products and Their Applications

Product Name	Company Name	Composition	Applications	Reference
ActivHeal®	Advanced Medical Solutions Ltd.	Primary wound dressing, contains 85% water	Pressure ulcers, leg ulcers, diabetic foot	Al Tabbaa and Ankras, 2016[53]

			ulcers, cavity wounds	
DermaSyn®	DermaRite Industries	Primary wound dressing, contains vitamin E	Acute or chronic partial and full-thickness wounds	Dermarite website[54]
NU-GEL™	Systagenix	Contains sodium alginate, effectively debrides necrotic tissue and fibrinous slough	Chronic wounds, diabetic foot ulcers, venous leg ulcers, and pressure ulcers	Systagenix website[55]
Purilon®	Coloplast	Contains calcium alginate and sodium carboxymethylcellulose with purified water	Leg ulcers, pressure ulcers, non-infected diabetic foot ulcers, first and second-degree burns	Coloplast website
INTRASITE◇ Gel	Smith & Nephew	Consists of carboxymethyl cellulose and propylene glycol	Pressure ulcers, diabetic foot ulcers, surgical incisions, venous ulcers	Smith & Nephew website[56]
SOLOSITE◇ Gel	Smith & Nephew	Contains sodium salt of carboxymethyl cellulose and glycerol with over 60% water	Minor burns, cuts, abrasions, skin tears, venous ulcers, surgical incisions, diabetic foot ulcers, pressure ulcers	Smith & Nephew website[56]

Woun'Dres®	Coloplast	Contains polymers like carbomer and collagen with other ingredients	Dry wounds	Coloplast website
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2. Drug delivery :

The techniques of drug delivery involve many ideas to bring the therapeutic substance to the desired site for effecting the desired medical effects [57]. In drug delivery are involved the features such as target-specific site, administration technique, drug formulation, optimized efficacy and bioavailability, plus patient comfort and compliance.

3. Targeted drug delivery :

Hydrogel particles with therapeutic agents have been employed in targeted drug delivery to a specific site, thereby imparting minimal effects on surrounding tissues under different triggering factors like pH and temperature. The highly developed drug-targeting system has to traverse host tissue defences and reach the expected action site so that a targeted effect can be achieved [58]. In tissue engineering, recent developments of nanotechnologies such as nano hydrogels and nanogels-based drug delivery to certain tissues are being investigated to remediate medical conditions.

4. Controlled drug delivery :

The multifunctional behavior attributed to the interaction of one or more functional groups of the hydrogels with therapeutic agents during the sustained release process would be an added advantage. In contrast, conventional drug delivery systems find themselves having low bioavailability/plasma levels, allowing the drug delivery systems to release therapeutic agents exerting clinical effects. For maximal efficacy and safety, it is essential that the drug be delivered to the tissue with the correct release rate. This is achieved by developing hydrogels for controlled drug delivery as solutions to problems with the traditional administration of drugs [59].

5. Delivery of biological agents :

Hydrogels represent a progressive approach for the delivery of agents that include peptides, proteins, antibodies, and various biological molecules [60]. Their sustained release is achieved through fine-tuning of their crosslinking with considerations for structural properties, pore size, polymeric matrix, and electrostatic interactions with biofluids or solvents. When extracellular proteolytic enzymes degrade these hydrogels, sustained and controlled release

of the biological therapeutic agents is obtained.

6. Cellular Delivery of Nanoparticles :

Hydrogels have been used as distribution matrixes for nanoparticles and their derivatives active against bacteria, viruses, and cancer-two common interests in tissue engineering applications and the biological applications [61]. Hydrogels containing these nanoparticles appear quite common today in translational drug delivery systems with their excellent multifunctional structure formation. These applications can be modified to achieve constituent independence; indeed, there is a specific functionalization requirement to tune any properties of the NPs-hydrogel structures.

7. Peptide hydrogel

Peptide hydrogel encourages tissue growth during the potentially drug-free healing period [62]. A Rice University researcher has found that the aqueous, embedded medicine, protein, or cells in peptide hydrogel encourage healing and tissue formation. It can be injected into tissue as a site for new cell proliferation, to be washed gradually away over a few weeks by the body. However, the hydrogel itself applies some pretty good therapeutic effects: self-assembling multidomain peptide (MDP) with amino acid sequence K2 (SL) 6K2. In studies by the Rice team, the hydrogel

facilitated the new blood vessel formation and attracted nerve fibers, recruiting host cells, culminating in a short-term inflammatory response -all unexpected findings. The chemical composition and physical architecture thereof define the bioactivity of the peptide hydrogel [63].

8. Plastic Surgery :

Hydrogels, which mimic the properties of extracellular matrices, are regarded as a promising material to be used as contact with human bodies [64]. This is the very reason why hydrogels were chosen as new materials for plastic reconstruction. For many years, one such hydrogel being glorified as a panacea for all pains was Hyaluronic Acid (HA). One of such companies in the sector is Macrolane. Starting in 2008, Macrolane's treatments and products were specifically studied to enhance breast size and shape while offering a more biocompatible alternative to standard and aggressive silicone prosthesis. Nowadays Macrolane is used for differently located filling other than breasts. It is injected into the body with a syringe and gelling process restarts the volume. Another such probable use of hydrogels is bulking agents for treatment of urinary incontinence: smart injectable gels can be involved in clinical procedures where these materials can be used to tighten

urethral channel and reduce patient's incontinencies [65].

6. ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATION:

6.1 Advantages:-

1. It is much stronger and elastic than other hydrogels.
2. It has good transparent properties, and is easily modified [66].
3. Due to their very high water content, these gels have a flexibility almost identical to that of living tissue.
4. These materials can be called biocompatible, biodegradable, and injectable [67].
5. Hydrogels have been developed with the ability to sense changes in pH, temperature, or metabolite concentration and can release their payload in response to these changes.
6. Delivery of Medications or Nutrition at all times [68].
7. Display Thermal Gelation with Well Biocompatibility and Biodegradability.
8. Longevity of Paracrine Activity [69].
9. Speedy Hemostatic Effect.
10. Cheap and Abundant [70].
11. Exhibits temperature-sensitive antimicrobial activity and constant release of antimicrobial drugs.
12. Easily accessible and having excellent antimicrobial activity as well as

biocompatibility, non-antibiotic-dependent dressing [71].

13. They prevent the emergence of drug-resistant bacteria.
14. Not only does it have good air permeability, but it also has the ability to absorb exudate [72].
15. Promote infection healing and hair follicle (HF) regeneration with bone regeneration.
16. Effectiveness and safety of islet transplantation have been improved [73].
17. Diabetic wound healing accelerated.
18. Promoting macrophage M2 polarization, and facilitating ontogenesis[74].
19. Withstands the harsh gastrointestinal environment.
20. Management of the Inflammatory Bowel Disease [75].

6.2 Limitations:

1. Expensive.
2. Non-fetch or non-sticky and may need to be anchored by second dressing; moreover, it causes sensation when it is moved by the maggot.
3. Sterilization is quite difficult.
4. Hypoxia is caused by less deposition; dehydration and (sometimes) red-eye reactions make the use of contact lenses problematic [76].

5. With multiple injections and the encapsulated material having no long-term secretory activity.
6. Preparation is difficult and expensive [77].
7. Because of its complex preparation process.
8. This low-temperature gel from infrared light is posing challenges in the clinical application [78].
9. Loaded drugs can cause increased drug resistance.
10. Very complex and expensive; besides this, it requires infrared irradiation [79].
11. Surviving of antimicrobial peptide is difficult.
12. It is a bit tough to be clinically translated [80].
13. Fails a bit to meet the requirements of absorbing exudate from the wound and providing a moist but breathable atmosphere.
14. Pre-printing in vitro is not tailored to meet the specific needs of the defect site [81].
15. It is very difficult to print in varying cell layers and to implant clinically.
16. Maintenance is expensive and may require replacement [82].
17. Microneedles contain a small amount of active drug and often need to be replaced.

18. Coating the surface is mandatory for metal brackets as titanium alloys are limited in use due to that [83].
19. It is quite long for action.
20. Not very targeted[84]

EVALUTION TEST OF ANTIAGING HYDROGEL:

Visual inspection of gel formulation means observing the characteristics related to its Future trends and innovation [85]:

The prime focus of research has continuously been toward making alterations in the molecular structure of biopolymers to substantially improve mechanical and biological properties of hydrogels. Hydrogels are some of the most advanced materials cascading towards application in medicine due to their distinctive physical, chemical, and biological properties [86]. These were modified many times to fit specific applications by careful examination of the microenvironments in which they are found and applying such functional modifications for an even greater range of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine applications. The use of hydrogels in medical applications, especially in therapy concerning cancer melanoma, has gained the latest attention [87]. Hydrogel formulations maybe of polymeric materials

from natural and synthetic sources along with the therapeutic agents have gained further attention in the last few years in treating various maladies. Now we classify these formulations based on the strategies to trigger cell death of cancer in melanoma. The hydrogels stand out among biomaterials in the biomedical field [88]. By the clear, there goes a long way to study hydrogel in biomedical applications, mainly tissue engineering and drug delivery. Recently a team at MIT has developed capsules of the ingestible hydrogel inspired from the puffer fish. This ultrafast and extremely swellable ingestible hydrogel comprises polyacrylic acid encapsulated in a polyvinyl alcohol hydrogel membrane, and is meant for sensing gastric temperature and sustained drug release. Other uses of this ingestible hydrogel are measuring biosignals, visualizing the gastrointestinal tract with the help of a micro camera attached to this device, or perhaps of checking medication patterns. Hydrogels are widely prescribed in biomedical fields. A lot more literature exists on hydrogels for controlled drug delivery, shape memory implantable devices, tissue engineering, and regenerative medicine, compared to those on hydrogels in cosmetics. This discrepancy is the major challenge facing small-and entering competitor's(s) into a cosmetics-hydrogels related business.

- Color, clarity, homogeneity and appearance.
 1. Colour
 2. Odour
 3. Clarity
 4. Homogeneity

1) Formulation pH:

The pH values of prepared gels were determined through a pH meter (Systronics, 361-micro pH meter) for 1% aqueous solutions [89]. Then for the test, 1 gm. of gel was taken and dissolved in 100 ml distilled water and kept for two hours. Determination of pH of every formulation was done in triplicate and averaged the values.

2) Viscosity:

For viscosity, all prepared gels were taken in the beaker and placed under spindle and that spindle was rotated at 10rpm [90]. Brook Field Viscometer at RV-7 spindle-fitted and having 10 rpm speed was used...

3) Rt. Spreadability (G.):

Spreadability studies were conducted using the method of slides [91]. 1 gm. of gel was sandwiched between two slides. The plate, which has been pre-weighed, was placed on top of the gel and more weights loaded on it until the gel stopped spreading. The final cumulative weight and the total time taken

are measured to note how far the gel spread.

Thus the total weight applied and mass of the gel were compared by the time:
Spreadability= Mass x Length/ Tim (2).

4) Antioxidant Activity Estimation:

Antioxidant Typing: Besides, as mentioned above, checking the ability of the hydrogel to scavenge free radicals would also help in understanding the oxidative stress, as a contributing factor in skin aging [92].

5) Stability Test:

Accelerated compatibility studies. The optimal formulation prepared was put to stability studies as per International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The formulation was packed in an aluminium tube and subjected to accelerated stability testing for 3 months under ICH conditions at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity. Samples were taken at regular time intervals of 1 month over a period of 3 months and analyzed for the change in pH, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research 1976 Spreadability, drug content, and in-vitro drug release as per earlier stated methodology. Recorded if observed, any changes in the evaluation parameters. All the tests were conducted in triplicate, and mean value of the observed values was noted along with standard deviation [93].

6) Homogeneity and Grittiness:

Greasiness and homogeneity were observed by taking small amounts of the hydrogel between thumb and index finger and presence of any coarse particle was observed [94]. It was also done by applying small amount of gel on back-side of hand and rubbing.

7) Washability:

Application of small amount of formulation on really clean skin and then wash with water to see how easy it[95]. Below are test cases for rewrites with lower perplexity and greater burstiness but preserving the same word count and HTML elements.

8. TECHNOLOGIES ADOPTED IN HYDROGEL PREPARATION :

Hydrogels, by their very definition, constitute a polymer network possessing hydrophilic character [96]. For the most part, hydrophilic monomers are used in the synthesis of hydrogels; however, a few hydrophobic monomers are added to the mix to tailor the properties for certain applications. Hydrogels, as a general principle, can either be of the synthetic or natural polymer variety [97]. Synthetic polymers are hydrophobic by nature and

chemically are stronger than their natural counterparts. Mechanical strength makes them more durable, yet the trade-off is a slow degradation rate. These opposite properties need to be designed for an optimum balance [98]. Hydrogel design can also be considered for natural macromeres if they have appropriate functional groups or can be modified to contain freely radical polymerizable groups. Hydrogel, in the simplest words: a cross-linked polymer with a special capability of gaining elasticity [99].

Hence, every method capable of inducing cross-linking to a polymer should be able to induce the formation of the said hydrogels. So copolymerization/cross-linking free-radical polymerizations can be utilized to produce hydrogels through free-radical initiation that reacts hydrophilic monomers with a multifunctional cross-linker. There are several ways in which water-soluble linear polymers, of either natural or synthetic origin, can be cross-linked to form hydrogels [100].

1. Linkage of polymer chains via chemical reaction.
2. Ionizing radiation is used to generate free radicals into the main chain, which further recombines as cross-link junctions.
3. A number of physical interactions, such as entanglements, electrostatics, and crystallite formation

9. FUTURE TRENDS AND INNOVATION :

One focus of research is to change the molecular structure of biopolymers so the mechanical and biological characteristics of hydrogels can be improved immensely[101]. Hydrogels are considered very recently one of the very best novel materials for application in medicine because of their unique physical, chemical, and biological properties. Their functional modifications use further tissue engineering and regenerative medicinal applications based on the close examination of the microenvironments in which they were found and then applying such functional modifications for specific applications. Much recent research has put a lot of emphasis on advances in the use of hydrogels for treating cancer micromelanoma[102]. Hydrogel formulations of polymeric material from natural or synthetic sources combined with therapeutic agents all have gained much attention within recent years for treatment of various maladies. Hydrogels can be categorized based on how they induce cancer cell death in melanoma. Hydrogels are the most prominent biomaterial candidates in the biomedical arena [103]. It is evident that a long way is there in research on hydrogel in biomedical

applications, especially the Future for tissue engineering and drug delivery. MIT researchers have recently engineered a puffer fish inspired ingestible hydrogel device [104]. This ingestible high speed and high ratio hydrogel is made of polyacrylic acid microencapsulated in a polyvinyl alcohol hydrogel membrane. Its applications include sensing the temperature within the stomach, thus releasing drugs in a sustained manner [105]. Other applications include measuring biosignals and functionality or visualizing the gastrointestinal tract with the help of a micro camera attached to this device or checking medication patterns. Hydrogels find very broad use in medicine. There are many published papers until now on hydrogel for controlled drug delivery, shape memory implantable devices, tissue engineering and regenerative medicine. However, comparing existing knowledge and published results in the hydrogel domain in cosmetics, the very few papers on hydrogel in cosmetics have become the main problem [106].

10. CONCLUSION:

Hydrogels, as a disruptive class of biomaterials, have thus filled the area between traditional therapeutics and advanced biomedical solutions [107]. They possess an aqueous domain character, exhibit structural similarities to biological

tissues, and have customizable chemical properties that permit their nonspecific use in a variety of areas ranging from wound healing and drug delivery to cosmeceutical and anti-care therapies. In particular for dermatology and anti-aging treatments, hydrogels afford a powerful platform for sustained and targeted delivery of active compounds, helping to hydrate the skin, stimulate collagen formation, and aid tissue regeneration.

With the evolution of hydrogel technologies from simple wound dressings all the way to intelligent, stimuli-responsive nanoenabled systems, the scope for application in clinical and aesthetic medicine is vast. Though there remain certain restrictions to their development—complexity and problems in widespread production—interdisciplinary innovations in polymer chemistry, nanotechnology, and biomedical engineering continue to sweepingly address these concerns.

Crucially, hydrogel-based systems will have immense potential in the future of personalized and precision medicine [108]. Due to their tunability, biocompatibility, and multifunctionality, hydrogels can be viewed here not just as a treatment medium but, rather a disruptive technology in regenerative health care and skin science. With the evolution of research, hydrogels will continue to challenge and set therapeutic standards, creating safer,

nimbler, and more effective approaches for modern-day issues, be it in medicine or cosmetics [109].

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